

Memory Neural Network Algorithm for Missile Control

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Abstract -Memory neural networks exhibit promising results for use as adaptive controllers for systems involving nonlinear time-delayed dynamics [1]. By associating a memory neuron to each network neuron, we alleviate the requirement for storing and recurrently feeding a nonlinear plant's past histories in order to adaptively control the system. Past attempts at designing a missile controller with a memory neural network produced encouraging results for the estimation facet of system modeling. [6] This paper presents the design and simulation of a model reference adaptive controller for a missile system using memory neural networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Neural networks can be used to solve highly nonlinear control problems such as the interception of a target by a missile [2-6]. Anderson [4] employs reinforcement and temporal-difference learning methods to design a system that balances an inverted pendulum on a cart. Nguyen and Widrow [3] apply the estimator/controller cascaded backpropagation scheme in controlling a truck to back up to a loading dock. Sastry et al. [2] apply the same technique and suggest a solution for feed-forward controllers and modify it by applying memory neuron networks.

In this work, we continue training a missile to intercept a target with an arbitrary trajectory by applying the latter method, which uses memory neuron networks. The object of the controller is to drive the missile's actual state to that of the reference target. Once the distance error between the two states is within the effective kill radius of the missile, it detonates. A *controller* learns to identify given target trajectories and the necessary control required to allow the missile to kill the target successfully. To train the controller, however, we implement another neural network that adequately models the nonlinear plant transfer function of the missile system. This neural network is the *estimator*. The estimator models the plant and allows backpropagation of the error through the total network. The backpropagated error, in turn, allows adjustment of the weights in the controller to provide the learning required to modify control parameters with changing target motion. The result of this work is a memory neuron network missile controller for nonlinear networks involving delay. The goal is to train a controller, allowing it to intercept a target with a trajectory previously unseen.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

The nonlinear plant is a missile with a $\frac{1}{s^2}$ transfer function. The control u varies from a laterally applied acceleration between 0 to 20 g's to either side of the missile. Later work adds missile aerodynamics, allowing the controller input to represent fin angle of the missile. The latter formulation is a more realistic method of implementing control. State variables identifying the missile and target plants include:

x_m = missile horizontal position,
 x_t = target horizontal position,
 y_m = missile vertical position,
 y_t = target vertical position,
 \dot{x}_m = missile horizontal velocity,
 \dot{x}_t = target horizontal velocity,
 \dot{y}_m = missile vertical velocity, and
 \dot{y}_t = target vertical velocity.

The neural network structure (see Fig. 1) resembles that used in [2,3]. The variables that apply to the neural networks are:

L = number of layers in a network,
N = network neurons per layer,
M = memory neurons per output network neuron,
x = input to a network neuron,
s = output of a network neuron,
v = output of a memory neuron,
w = weight connecting network neurons between layers,
f = weight connecting memory neuron to next layer network neuron,
 α = input weight to a memory neuron,
 β = weight connecting memory neuron to its output network neuron, and
g(x) = activation function of a neuron.

Details of the design of the memory neurons within the input, hidden, and output layers contained in [2-6] provide a useful algorithm for updating output values and weights. The memory neuron receives the output of its associated neuron and its own feedback signal defined below. The self feedback allows a weighted accumulation of the past neural

activity at that processing element. The memory neuron feeds its output to the next layer network neurons in the same manner as its source network neuron.

Traditionally, the input to a hidden or output layer neuron is [3,6]

$$\bar{x}_{i+1} = \bar{s}_i \bar{w}_i \quad (1)$$

where i indicates the layer number. However, with additional outputs from previous layer memory neurons, the input becomes

$$\bar{x}_{i+1} = \bar{w}_i \bar{s}_i + \bar{f}_i \bar{v}_i, \quad (2)$$

and the input to the output layer neuron is further extended by

$$\bar{x}_{i+1} = \bar{w}_i \bar{s}_i + \bar{f}_i \bar{v}_i + \bar{\beta}_i \bar{v}_i. \quad (3)$$

These last two equations show where the effect of the memory neurons takes place. Since the output s of any neuron is a function of its input

$$\bar{s}_i = g(\bar{x}_i), \quad (4)$$

each of these additional memory neuron values, which contain historical data of the related network neuron, will affect the output proportionally to the weight derived through learning. The activation functions $g(x)$ chosen for the hidden and output layers [2], respectively, are

$$g_1(\bar{x}) = \frac{c_1}{1 + \exp(-k_1 \bar{x})}, \quad (5)$$

$$g_2(\bar{x}) = c_2 \frac{1 - \exp(-k_2 \bar{x})}{1 + \exp(-k_2 \bar{x})}. \quad (6)$$

The memory neural network recursively weights the history, and the output of the memory neuron is

$$\bar{v}_i(k) = \bar{\alpha}_i(k) \bar{s}_i(k-1) + (1 - \bar{\alpha}_i(k)) \bar{v}_i(k-1) \quad (7)$$

We include time k in the notation to isolate which values and weights are dependent on past time quantities. Note that required past values of the total network input and output do not have to be stored in memory as they must be with traditional "look back" smoothing control schemes such as the extended Kalman filter.

With the calculations of neuron input and output values understood, it is now important to determine how to update the weights to perform backpropagation of error. Once the output layer values are calculated, the resulting s_i are called the estimates of the plant output. We call this estimate \hat{y}_i .

Figure 1. Memory neural network controller architecture.

The squared error between the estimate and the actual plant output is:

$$e = \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} (\hat{y}_j - y_j)^2 \quad (8)$$

where j indicates which neuron's output value (state variable estimate) is being compared to the plant state variable.

Backpropagation of this error through the network is now possible. Weight updates [2] for time $k+1$ are

$$\bar{w}_i(k+1) = \bar{w}_i(k) - \eta \bar{e}_{i+1}(k) \bar{s}_i(k) \quad (9)$$

$$\bar{f}_i(k+1) = \bar{f}_i(k) - \eta \bar{e}_{i+1}(k) \bar{v}_i(k) \quad (10)$$

The i th layer weights depend on the $(i+1)$ layer errors that are backpropagated and the previous value of the i th layer weights. Additionally, we weight past outputs of the network and memory neurons by step factor η . The memory neuron weights α and β are updated using chain-rule approximations of the differential error with respect to that weight.

III. RESULTS

We chose two different networks, each with three layers. The first network consisted of six hidden layer neurons and one memory neuron associated with each output network neuron (6:1). The other had three hidden layer neurons and no memory neurons in the output layer network neuron (3:0). The (6:1) system gave quite favorable results in the initial estimator training. Estimator training took place for 1000 epochs with a control input of zero, 1000 epochs with a random uniform control input, and 1000 epochs with a sinusoidal control input. State variables were random over the scaled ranges for position and velocity. The altitude varied to 5000 feet (the target at 3000 feet) and the range

limit on the horizontal was 30,000 feet. Each epoch trained over a two second interval of sequences spaced by a time step of .01 second. Thus, the estimator reacts to 200 sequences of states and control *each epoch*, for a total of 600,000 time steps. Initially, we gave equal weight to the position and the velocity errors. This caused poor convergence for the position error and good results for the velocity error. We made a key change to favor the position error over the velocity error in the weight updates. Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show velocity error improvement with increased training time. Each initial surge in the velocity plots indicates a new random sequence. The subsequent tapering to zero shows how quickly the estimator minimizes its difference with the actual missile plant. Training the controller off-line decreases the time required to update weights. No adjustment of estimator weights occurs during this phase, and the outputs of the actual missile plant need not be calculated since the estimator should accurately model the plant. Controller training, unlike the estimator, tailors its

objective directly to the target intercept problem. The cost function to minimize was the difference between target state and missile state.

Training the controller on-line allows the estimator to continue learning much like a traditional adaptive controller.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Estimator training in this system proved to be excellent. The use of memory neurons proved to be a viable method by which to train this two neural network system. Controller training, however, was not optimal in this case. The tendency in the system was to overshoot the trajectory of the missile. The controller net performed much better as a velocity predictor than a position predictor. From this point, there exist two major areas of study which vary in complexity. The first is to emphasize position error in our weighting of neural values through the network. This can be performed by using weighting coefficients on the backpropagated errors in order to allow the position values and weights to dominate. The other direction of study is to analyze the positive effects of including acceleration. The addition of two more state variables in the target and missile complicate the problem, yet the same principles apply. Only the network structure changes. Similarly, the coefficients associated with acceleration must be fully understood in order to optimize learning and performance of the controller.

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Figure 2. Snapshot of estimator velocity error early in training cycle.

Figure 3. Snapshot of estimator velocity error after sufficient training.